

Acacia Catechu Methanolic Extract as a Remedy for Wounds - An *in Vitro* Approach

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ABSTRACT

Wound healing is a multifactorial process which includes inflammation, tissue proliferation, and remodeling. Plant therapeutics are becoming increasingly valuable in wound care because they are cost-effective with fewer side effects. This *in vitro* study explores the wound healing, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and antioxidant activities of the methanolic extract of *Acacia catechu* bark (ACME). Phytochemical characterization using DPPH radical scavenging, UV-Vis, and FTIR spectroscopy has identified the presence of phenolic and functional bioactive groups with strong antioxidant potential. ACME has been found to possess significant antibacterial activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, a common wound pathogen. The anti-inflammatory property of ACME was confirmed by the reduction of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α and IL-6) and elevation of anti-inflammatory cytokines (IL-10 and TGF- β) in LPS-stimulated RAW 264.7 cells. The antioxidant activity was confirmed by the reduction of Reactive Oxygen Species and NO synthesis. ACME also enhanced the major indicators of wound repair, like the fibroblast cell migration and collagen deposition in scratch assays and Sirius red staining. The findings of this study reveal the potential of *Acacia catechu* methanolic extract as a promising natural therapeutic agent for wound healing.

KEYWORDS: *Acacia catechu*, Antimicrobial, Anti-inflammatory, Antioxidant, Reactive Oxygen Species, Collagen deposition, Wound healing

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I. INTRODUCTION

Wounds are an inevitable aspect of life, varying widely in type and requiring precise therapeutic strategies. There are different types of wounds, and they may require various treatments (Thakur et al., 2011). A wound can be described as any disruption in the normal anatomical structure of any tissue and its loss of function (Lazarus et al., 1994). Among these skin wounds are of serious concern as the skin is the largest organ and a critical barrier of the human body. Thus, many studies have focused on the skin wound healing process (Guo and Dipietro 2010). Wound healing is a dynamic and highly regulated process, which includes a cascade of events such as haemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodelling (Sharma, Zakka, and Mihm 2017), which may take days to years to repair the damaged tissues. This complex biological event is a complete interplay of growth

factors, cells and cytokines and ends up in the complete closure of wounds (Krafts 2010).

The body's defence mechanism, inflammation, aims to get rid of the source of cell damage. But occasionally, it can also spiral out of control and exacerbate inflammation (Soonthornsit et al., 2017). Impaired wound healing often results from the variation of actions of cytokine, growth factors, cellular and extracellular components and some proteases. This dysregulation can cause a high deposition of collagen and abnormal scar formation (Enoch and Leaper 2006). Factors, such as microbial infection, low blood circulation level and diabetic conditions can impact the management of wounds and can escalate the treatment cost (Thakur et al., 2011).

A well-orchestrated sequence of overlapping, interdependent physiological processes lead to the healing of acute wounds. In younger individuals, this sequence may

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take several days, whereas, for adults, it may take several weeks. In less than four weeks, the majority of wounds heal without complications and restore essential skin functions such as barrier integrity, pliability, and homeostasis. Various systemic conditions including diabetes, vascular disease, hyperglycemia, ischemia, and neuropathy, can disrupt the normal process, leading to non-healing or chronic wounds. A common way to characterize a wound is to identify its underlying cause: pressure ulcers, arterial leg ulcers, venous leg ulcers, and diabetic foot ulcers (Shedoeva et al., 2019). Delayed wound healing represents a significant global health challenge nowadays, mainly in diabetic patients (Reinke and Sorg 2012) and underscores the urgent need for cost-effective and natural therapeutic alternatives. Currently, 6 million people are suffering from chronic wounds worldwide.

Only a small percentage of the many medicinal plants that have been used traditionally to treat wounds have been the subject of thorough scientific study. Numerous antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing qualities of plant-derived compounds are reported in the literature, but many are still underexplored. To validate their traditional claims and to develop standardized, safe, efficacious, and widely accepted herbal formulations for wound healing, several pharmacological studies on plants have used diverse wound healing models and investigated their underlying molecular mechanisms (Thakur et al., 2011).

Acacia catechu (*Senegalia catechu*) is a deciduous plant native to South Asia and Southeast Asia including the Indian Subcontinent. It thrives in both natural and plantation vegetation in almost all areas of our country up to a height of about 1300m from sea level. The bark of *Acacia catechu* has been used widely for various medicinal uses for many decades like colds, cough, diarrhoea, milk production in pregnant ladies and so on and it shows antihelmintic, anti-inflammatory and antipyretic properties (Singh and Lal 2006; Sunil et al., 2019). In recent years, numerous studies have examined various pharmacological properties of extracts prepared from heartwood, bark, leaves, and seeds of different *Acacia* species. These species have shown considerable wound-healing activity. The heartwood extract is also used for skin afflictions, bronchitis, ulcers, psoriasis, gum troubles, anaemia, sores and stomatitis (Sunil et al., 2019). Based on these attributes, the present study was designed to investigate the anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, and wound-healing potential of *Acacia catechu* bark extracts.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials

Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) was brought from Sigma and Antibiotic-antimycotic solution, and FBS were procured from Gibco. The methanol used was from Merck. All other reagents used were of the analytical or equivalent grade. The bark of *Acacia catechu* was collected from Government Ayurveda College Poojappura, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala

B. Preparation of Plant Extract

The plant materials were thoroughly washed, removed all the dirt and dried in the shade. The dried plant materials were stored at room temperature, finally, ground plants were soaked in methanol separately for 3 days at cold conditions (4°C). The crude extract was concentrated by a rotary evaporator (Heidolph intelligent evaporation). The remaining methanol was evaporated by using a desiccator. These crude extracts were used for further investigation.

C. Characterization of Plant Extract

1) Total Radical Scavenging Activity by DPPH (2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl) Assay: The DPPH assay was based on the procedure of (Kiranmai, Kumar, and Ibrahim 2011). 2 mL reaction mixture containing 1 ml of plant extract of various concentrations (200-1000 µg/mL) and 1 mL DPPH was incubated for 30 minutes at 37°C and absorbance was read at 517 nm.

$$\text{DPPH Scavenging Activity} = [(A_0 - A_1) / A_0] * 100$$

A₀- Absorbance of Control, A₁- Absorbance of sample

2) Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy: Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) was performed to identify the characteristic functional groups present in the plant extracts. A small quantity of the *Acacia catechu* methanolic extract (ACME) was mixed in dry potassium bromide (KBr) separately. The mixture was mixed in a mortar and pressed at a pressure of 6 bars within 2 min to form a KBr thin disc. Then the disc was placed in a sample cup of a diffuse reflectance accessory. The IR spectrum was obtained using an FTIR spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer LS-55 - Luminescence spectrometer, USA). The sample was scanned from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹. The peak values of FTIR were recorded (Amrutha et al., 2021)

3) UV-Visible Spectra: The UV-visible spectra of ACME were recorded using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Eppendorf) in a range of 200 to 800 nm using a microcuvette of 1 mm pathlength and the graph was plotted using Origin software

4) Anti-Microbial Activity: The Agar Well Diffusion Method as described in European pharmacopoeia with slight modification was used for antibacterial testing (James et al., 2011; Walker 1999). Sterile MHA plates were used for the test. Wells were cut using a sterile well bore of 8 mm diameter. Freshly sub-cultured bacterial strains (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) were suspended in one ml Nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 2 hours to obtain log phase cultures, opacity was checked with 0.5 McFarland turbidity standards (approximately 1 to 2 x 10⁸ colony forming units per ml). 100 µl of the pure cultures of test strains were swabbed uniformly using a sterile swab on the surface of the MHA plate to obtain an even inoculum. The plates were allowed to dry for 5 minutes and 100 µl of different concentrations of the sample, DMSO and standard drug were transferred to each well. The antibacterial activity was observed after incubating the plates for 24 hours at 37°C

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and the zone of inhibition surrounding the well was noted in mm.

D. In vitro Anti-inflammatory effect

1) RAW 264.7 cell lines in Direct contact with ACME: For this assay, RAW 264.7 cell lines were seeded at a density of 5000 cells/well in 96-well plates in DMEM High Glucose, supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS). After 24 hrs of incubation, the cells were treated with different concentrations of the extracts (5,10,25,50 and 100 µg/ml respectively). Then after 24 hours, culture media were aspirated and the cells were washed with Phosphate-Buffered Saline (PBS). Then 20 µL of the MTT solution (5 mg/mL) was added to each well. After 4 hrs of incubation, the media were removed and purple crystals were dissolved in solubilizing solution. Absorbance in each well was measured at 570 nm using an ELISA reader (epoch ELISA) (Mitra et al., 2016)

$$\text{Percentage Viability} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of Treated Cells}}{\text{Absorbance of Untreated Cells}} * 100$$

2) Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA): For ELISA total protein was quantified by using Lowery's method (LOWRY et al., 1951). Indirect ELISA was performed using specific antibodies (TNF α, IL-6, IL-10 and Tgf- β). Cell culture medium after 24-hour treatment with ACME (10µg/ml) and LPS (1µg/ml) was precoated onto ELISA plates served as the antigen. O-dianisidine was used as substrate and the absorbance of the coloured horse radish peroxidase (HRP) product was measured spectrophotometrically at 405 nm by an Epoch microplate reader (Shalini et al., 2016)

3) Confocal Microscopy for ROS Detection: RAW 264.7 cells were seeded at a concentration of 1*10⁶ cells per well in a cover slip placed in a six-well plate. After 24-hour ACME was treated in one of the groups and kept for another 24 hours. The ROS reaction was created according to Image ITTM- LIVE Green ROS Detection Kit (I36007). Then the confocal images of the coverslips in which cells were grown were taken using a Nikon A1R Confocal Microscope at RGCB, Thiruvananthapuram.

E. In vitro Cell Migration Assay

1) L929 cells in Direct contact with Extract and Cell viability Assay: For this assay, L929 cell lines were seeded at a density of 5000 cells/well in 96-well plates in DMEM High Glucose, supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS). After 24 hrs of incubation, the cells were treated with different concentrations of the extracts (5,10,25,50,100,125 and 150µg/ml respectively). Then after 24hrs, MTT was carried out in the same procedure described in D.1.

2) Scratch Wound Assay: The cell migration of fibroblast cells in the presence of ACME was assessed by a scratch assay. A monolayer of cells was formed after cells were

planted in 24 well culture plates at a density of 1×10⁴ cells per well. Using an autoclaved tip, a sharp scratch was softly scraped through the monolayer. The cells were rinsed with 1 ml of PBS to clear away the debris and soften the edges of the scratch. The growing medium was carefully added to the wells after adding the sample ACME at a concentration of 100 µg/ml (n=3), and the wells were then placed in the incubator. Using a phase-contrast microscope, the migration of cells toward filling gaps was observed at various time intervals, and pictures were recorded. Then ImageJ software was used to calculate the % wound closure.

$$\% \text{ Wound Closure} = \left[\frac{\text{gap distance } t_0 - \text{gap distance } t_n}{\text{gap distance } t_0} \right] * 100$$

t₀- Time 0 hour, t_n- nth time interval

3) Collagen Deposition: Fibroblast cells were seeded on 6 well plates (1×10⁶ cells/well) and were incubated overnight at 37 °C and 5% CO₂ atmosphere. After incubation, an extract of ACME was added in different wells at a concentration of 100µg/ml to the cells. Sirius red assay was done after 48 hours of incubation. After removing the media, 1 ml of Sirius red reagent was added, and the mixture was kept under mild shaking for 20 min. The stain was removed and the cell layer was dissolved in 0.2 ml sodium hydroxide (0.1 N NaOH) and the obtained solution was read at 550 nm. Stained untreated cells were used to compare the results.

4) Nitric Oxide Assay: 100 µg/mL concentration of ACME and H₂O₂ (100 µM) were added to L929 fibroblasts and after incubation cell lysate was prepared by centrifuging the samples using lysis buffer (0.1 M Tris, 0.25 M EDTA, 2M NaCl and 0.5% Triton X 100, pH 8). NO production was estimated as the level of nitrite in the cell lysate using Griess reaction (Leiro et al., 2007)

F. Statistical Analysis

Each experiment was performed at least three times. Data were analyzed by one-way ANOVA. Differences at the 95% level were considered to be significant. Normality, homogeneity of variances and data independence were evaluated before all the analyses. Statistical Analysis Comparison between groups was made by One-Way Analysis of Variance for the vascular densities and morphometry by Graphpad Prism v.5. Differences with P <0.05 between experimental groups were considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A. DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay

The extract ACME showed a good Antioxidant capacity during the DPPH Radical Scavenging Assay. The concentrations 200-1000 µg/mL possess the scavenging activity above 80%. The graph is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: DPPH Scavenging Activity. The DPPH radical scavenging activity of ACME was increased with increase in concentration. There was no significant difference between the groups.

B. FTIR

The peaks of functional groups present in ACME are figured out in Figure 2 (a) and functional groups are depicted in table 1. The peak at 3347 cm⁻¹ corresponds to -OH stretching. The peak at 2926 cm⁻¹ corresponds to strong O-H and N-H stretching and weak -CH stretching. 1693,1640 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of strong C=O and CO-O-CO stretching, medium C=N stretching and weak C-H bending. 1515,1448,1371,1251,1160 and 1045 cm⁻¹.

Table 1: Functional groups present in FTIR spectra of ACME

Wave Number (cm ⁻¹)	Functional Group
3347	O-H Stretching - Phenols or Alkaloids
2926	C-H Stretching - Aliphatic hydrocarbons
1693	C=O Stretching- Carbonyl groups
1604-1504	C=C Stretching - Aromatic rings or Amide bending
1039	C-O Stretching – Alcohol, Ether, Ester

C. UV-Visible Spectroscopy

The UV- spectra Figure 2 (b) showed peaks at 206,226,286 and 311 nm respectively which indicates the presence of sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen which are present in the secondary metabolites.

Figure 2: FTIR and UV Visible Spectra of ACME showing different functional groups. a) FTIR, b) UV Visible spectra

D. Anti-Microbial Activity

Anti-microbial activity by disc diffusion method is depicted in Figure 3, which showed an inhibitory effect of ACME on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The extract showed a maximum of 12- and 13-mm diameter zone of inhibition in 150 and 200 mg/ml concentration respectively on the strain when compared with Streptomycin which showed a 12 mm diameter zone of inhibition. The DMSO control showed no effect on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. From the result, it could be said that the extract has a good capability to control the activity of microbes in wound conditions since the selected microbe is associated with an infectious wound.

Figure 3: Antimicrobial activity of ACME on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Table 2: Zone of inhibition of ACME on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Concentration of ACME (mg/mL)	Zone of inhibition on <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (mm in diameter)
Streptomycin	12
DMSO	NA
50 mg/mL	10
100 mg/mL	11
150 mg/mL	12
200 mg/mL	13

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E. MTT Cytotoxicity Assay: ACME in direct contact with RAW 264.7 cell lines

The cytotoxicity assay of ACME (Figure 4) showed maximum cell viability at 5 and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentrations. All other concentrations were non-toxic compared with negative control (30% ethanol). From the above concentrations, 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ was selected for further anti-inflammatory and antioxidant studies.

Figure 4: MTT Assay of ACME on RAW 264.7 cell lines.

The maximum viability was showed at 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration of the extract. There was no significant difference between the groups.

F. ELISA

The ELISA results (Figure 6) of Pro and Anti-Inflammatory cytokines indicate the anti-inflammatory activity of ACME on LPS-induced inflammation. In the results, it is clear that the pro-inflammatory cytokine levels (TNF- α and IL-6) are decreased in ACME-treated groups and Anti-inflammatory cytokines IL-10 and TGF- β levels increased in ACME-treated groups in 24-hour treatment. In all results, $P < 0.05$.

Figure 5: Protein levels of Pro and Anti-inflammatory cytokines. Protein levels of a) TNF- α , b) IL-6, c) TGF- β , d) IL-10 calculated by ELISA and expressed as OD units/mg protein. The levels of pro inflammatory cytokines were decreased and anti-inflammatory cytokines were increased in ACME treated group compared with LPS. *- significant difference compared with untreated group where

*- $P < 0.05$, **- $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$. #- significant difference between LPS treated group, ##- $P < 0.01$, ###- $P < 0.001$.

G. ROS Generation

The ROS assay revealed the antioxidant activity of ACME against TBHP. The results in the figure 6 show differences in ROS (reactive oxygen species) generation among three groups. The untreated control group (a) exhibits minimal fluorescence, indicating low basal levels of ROS. The TBHP-treated group (b) displays intense green fluorescence, signifying a substantial increase in ROS due to oxidative stress. The third group, treated with the plant extract after TBHP exposure, shows reduced fluorescence compared to TBHP alone treated group.

Figure 6: Reactive Oxygen Species generation in TBHP treated RAW 264.7 cells. The ROS generation was decreased in ACME treated groups (c) compared with TBHP alone treated group (b).

H. Cytotoxicity assay of ACME on L929 cell lines

The cytotoxicity assay of ACME on L929 cell lines showed maximum viability of cells at 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration. All other concentrations were nontoxic since they showed viability greater than 50% which is depicted in figure 7.

Figure 7: MTT assay of ACME on L929 fibroblasts. Maximum cell viability was shown at 100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration, which was selected for further studies

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I. Scratch Wound Assay

The Scratch Wound Assay demonstrated the potential of ACME as a wound-healing triggering phytochemical. The ACME-treated wound healed 99.99% whereas the untreated cells healed only 85% in 48 hours. These findings are illustrated in figure 8.

Figure 8: Scratch wound Assay on L929 cells- a) Phase contrast microscoping images of scratch wound healing in different time intervals, b) graphical representation of % wound healing. *- significant difference from the untreated groups, where $P < 0.05$

J. Collagen Estimation

A collagen estimation assay was carried out to study the remodelling phase of wound healing and the results show a significant difference in the amount of collagen deposition between the untreated and ACME-treated group in 48-hour treatment. The inverted phase contrast microscopic images also visually confirmed the results. The representative images distinctly illustrate the difference in the amount of collagen (figure 9).

Figure 9: Collagen Deposition by sirius red assay. a)- 10x phase contrast microscopic images of L929 cells b)- graphical representation of amount of collagen in UG. **- significant difference between untreated group where $P < 0.01$

K. Nitric Oxide Assay

Nitric Oxide Assay revealed the anti-oxidant Activity of ACME on L929 cell lines. The NO levels were elevated in the H₂O₂ treated cells which was decreased in ACME treated cells. The result is shown in figure 10.

Figure 10: Nitric Oxide Level. Level of Nitric Oxide in H₂O₂ induced L929 fibroblast cells where the NO levels were decreased in ACME treated cells. **-Significant difference from untreated group, $P < 0.01$, ###- significant difference from H₂O₂ treated group, $P < 0.001$

III. DISCUSSION

Wound healing is a complex biological process that progresses through four distinct but overlapping stages:- Haemostasis, inflammation, proliferation and remodelling. These phases are controlled by intricate signalling pathways and cytokines. Plant-derived therapies have long been utilized in traditional medicine for wound management. In many cultures, tribal and folklore medicine uses a variety of herbs to cure burns and wounds. These organic substances promote tissue regeneration and repair via a variety of mechanisms (Thakur et al., 2011)

In our study, we examined the anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial and wound-healing activity of *Acacia catechu* bark methanolic extracts. It has been demonstrated to play a variety of roles in the treatment of illnesses like leprosy, sore throats, gingivitis, colitis, dysentery, stomach issues, asthma, cough, renal issues, and dental and oral infections (Negi and Dave 2010; Rahmatullah et al., 2013; Sunil et al., 2019). In the food, textile, cosmetic, and soft drink sectors, gum exudates from *Acacia* species have been widely employed as demulcents, emulsifiers, adhesives, and stabilizers (Shen et al., 2006; Stohs and Bagchi 2015). This context included the in vitro methods for finding out the different properties of *Acacia catechu*.

Reactive Oxygen Species are very harmful or dangerous to the wound healing process since they cause tissue damage or cell death at the site of infection (Aliyev et al., 2004). The compounds or plants which have the free radical scavenging

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activity can be used for the cure of wounds. Plants with free radical scavenging properties can play a pivotal role in facilitating wound repair. In our study, the DPPH Radical Scavenging assay revealed the potent antioxidant activity of ACME as a scavenger of free radicals. Every concentration selected in the assay has a scavenging activity above 80% on DPPH (figure 1).

The FTIR spectrum of ACME (Figure 2 (a)) identified various functional groups, including alcohol, alkyne, carboxylic acid, amine salt, alkane, aromatic compound, conjugated ketone, imine/oxime, anhydride and fluoro compound. The absence of any peak at the 2260 nm area revealed the absence of the cyanide group in the extract, a crucial aspect of the plants' benign nature (Chunduri and Shah 2016). The UV Visible Spectra of ACME (figure 2 (b)) showed peaks between 200 and 400 nm which is a clear indication of groups such as S, O, N (Njoku et al., 2013) which are the structural components of secondary metabolites. The major peaks obtained in the UV Spectra of ACME were 206, 226, 286 and 311. In a study conducted by Fathima and M 2018, they highlighted that the peaks ranging from 280 to 330 nm are a feature of phenolic groups. According to the reference we can mention that our plant extract also contains the phenolic groups.

Open wounds are highly susceptible to microbial invasion, particularly from bacteria, and can serve as a portal for systemic illnesses. In addition to healing more slowly, infected wounds frequently create toxic substances and unpleasant exudates, which also kill the cells that are responsible for regeneration. A traditional remedy's antibacterial and antifungal ingredients may stop this from happening, which may be why it's used to treat wounds (Houghton et al., 2005). The major Microbes that attack the wounded site are *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Aqueous extracts of *Acacia catechu* exhibited an antimicrobial effect against Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Adhikari, Aryal, and Bhattarai 2021). ACME demonstrated effective antibacterial activity on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with a diameter of 10 and 11 mm in 50 and 100 mg/mL concentrations respectively against streptomycin (figure 3).

Chronic inflammation is a major issue faced during wound healing which may cause a delay in healing and make the wound chronic. Potent anti-inflammatory agents are essential for the treatment of wounds. Sunil et al., 2019 revealed the anti-inflammatory effect of *Acacia catechu* Ethanollic and Water Extracts. The TNF α production was decreased and IL-10 production levels were increased. In our study, we examined the production of TNF α , IL-6, IL-10 and Tgf- β in LPS-induced RAW 264.7 cell lines treated with ACME. The results showed the inflammation-reducing potential of the plant.

The exact balance between low and high ROS levels is crucial for determining the functional outcome: although excessive

ROS release leads to cellular damage and impaired wound repair (Ponugoti et al., 2013), low levels of ROS are necessary for effective wound healing (Rodriguez et al., 2008). During the study, we created excess ROS generation by the application of TBHP (tert-butyl hydroperoxide) on RAW 264.7 macrophage cell lines and the fluorescence image was taken. The treatment with TBHP induced significant ROS generation, indicating oxidative stress, which was markedly reduced upon treatment with the plant extract, demonstrating its antioxidant and cytoprotective potential. This aligns with findings from similar studies where plant-derived extracts have shown efficacy in mitigating TBHP-induced oxidative damage by scavenging reactive oxygen species and improving cellular antioxidant defenses (Lee Sion Mi et al., 2014).

Successful wound healing needs the coordination of various cell types, including fibroblasts, keratinocytes and endothelial cells. Therefore, we examined whether ACME application on scratch wound enhances cell migration or not. The results were satisfying since with ACME treatment nearly complete wound closure (100%) was observed within 48 hours compared with the untreated group and it was clear that the plant has the wound healing potential. The application of matrix materials and their subsequent evolution over time comprise the remodelling phase of wound repair. During repair, dermal macromolecules like collagen, fibronectin, hyaluronic acid, and proteoglycans are deposited and act as a scaffold for cellular migration and tissue support (Peacock 1980). Collagen deposition is critical for wound healing and restoring structural integrity (Buffoni et al., 1993). The collagen deposition on L929 cell lines was checked in different cell groups via Sirius red assay and found that ACME increases the collagen deposition. ACME was most promising in inhibiting H₂O₂-induced NO production in L929 fibroblast cell lines. To our knowledge, this is the first comprehensive in vitro study demonstrating the wound healing potential of *Acacia catechu* methanolic bark extract through antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and fibroblast-stimulating mechanisms.

IV. CONCLUSION

The methanolic extract of *Acacia catechu* bark exhibited significant antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial and wound healing activity in all the experiments conducted by *in vitro* methods. Future investigations should focus on identifying specific bioactive compounds and, the ability of the extract to activate the major signalling cascades involved in the process of wound healing. The findings of the present study shed light on the potential of ACME as a promising, cost-effective, plant-based therapeutic for the treatment of both acute and chronic wounds, by targeting underlying molecular mechanisms.

V. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Amrutha Dileepkumar.Sreejakumari: Data collection, Experiments, figure creation, article writing. Abhirami Sunthi and Mani Sebastian: Article writing, figure creation. Maya Gopi Pillai; Article writing, editing. Helen Antony: Conceptualization, Project administration, Editing and final drafting, Corresponding author.

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